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Research Article

FACTORS AND PERSONAL FEATURES OF ARROWS, AS A FACTOR OF RELIABILITY OF THEIR ACTIVITIES. BASIC TYPES AND PROPERTIES OF ATTENTION AS ONE OF THE COMPONENTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL RELIABILITY AT ARROW ATHLETES.¹Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova, ²Oxana Y. Ilyakhina, ³Nikolay N. Severin, ⁴Sergey S. Klimenko, ⁵Sergey A. Ermolenko, ⁶Vladimir A. Goncharov¹Belgorod Law Institute of Ministry of the Internal of the Russian Federation named after I.D. Putilin 308024 71, Gorkogo Str., Belgorod, Russia, Katya260688@mail.ru**Article Received:** August 2019**Accepted:** September 2019**Published:** October 2019**Abstract:**

The problem of reliability in sports has become one of the most important achievements in the practice of sports of the highest achievements in the last 20 years. The problem of reliability in sports arose in connection with the increase in the social significance of sports, which manifested itself, first of all, in a change in the attitude of society towards sports and athletes, in increasing requirements for their professional, moral, and moral training. The immanent development of sports also required an increase in the intensity of physical and mental stress. As a result, the reliability problem in extreme competition conditions has been highlighted in recent years. It is known that at the Olympic Games, victory requires extreme or near-ultimate efforts from athletes. And it is achieved by one who has a greater supply of strong-willed energy and a higher level of psychological stability, who is able to mobilize moral and physical resources in a decisive moment or, on the contrary, for a rather long time. Reliability is generally one of the most important categories in sports. It is difficult precisely because there is no dizzying take-off in it followed by a very painful fall, there is no brightness of a short flash, there is no ambitious "I", that same "I", in which self-esteem (always with a plus sign) flashes on the "scoreboard of self-confidence" before than there will be an objective assessment of others.

One of the main reasons for the emergence of the reliability problem in sports is a sharp increase in the volume and intensity of physical and mental stress as a result of the immanent development of sports and the growth of records. Suffice it to say that if 30-40 years ago, athletes trained, as a rule, several months a year, but now - all year round. Previously, they practiced 2 times a week, now 2, or even 3 times a day.

Keywords: sports activity, reliability, reliability problem, sports, internal attention, high level, mental reliability, principle of self-regulation, attention, immanent development of sports, unintentional activation of attention, sportsman's mental reliability, sense organ.

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INTRODUCTION:

Significant reasons for the emergence of the reliability problem in sports include the development of sports science itself. The process of development of science can be characterized by the establishment and expansion of relations between individual branches of science, expressed in the optimal solution to the most pressing problems of practice, carried out, as a rule, at the intersections of sciences, within the framework of a systematic, integrated, interdisciplinary approach. Such a trend contributes to the emergence of the so-called meta-sciences, any component of which does not have its own significance outside the context of the problems associated with their sciences. The problem of reliability in sports has become especially urgent in recent years. She is devoted to the study of a number of scientists - V.V. Davydov, V.M. Dyachkova, T.T. Dzhamgarova, N.A. Khudadova, V.V. Kossova, A.V. Rodionova, V.A. Vyatkina, A.D. Ganyushkina, A.A. Lyalayana and others. Thus, the emergence and development of the theory of reliability in sports is due to a number of reasons of an objective and subjective nature, the importance of which is increasing more and more every year, and the need for theoretical and methodological development of this important scientific and applied problem also increases.

The development of the conceptual apparatus is one of the main and important processes for developing the theory of reliability of systems in general and in sports in particular.

Purpose of the study:

The goal of our work is explanation factors and personal features of arrows, as reliability factors of their activities and determining the components of psychological reliability of arrows.

RESEARCH METHODS:

The following research methods were used in our work:

1. Analysis and synthesis of scientific and methodological literature.
2. Pedagogical observation.
3. Pedagogical questioning of trainers and athletes.
4. Testing.
5. Pedagogical experiment.
6. Questioning.
7. Methods of mathematical statistics.
8. Analysis and interpretation of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A careful examination of the proposed definitions of reliability in sports made it possible to combine them into four groups according to the subject of the study.

1 group of definitions refers to the definitions of the reliability of competitive activity of athletes (regardless of sport). L.P. Matveev (1977), under the "reliability" of the actions of athletes in competitions, understands the comprehensive result of improving his skills and abilities, guaranteeing high effectiveness of actions in spite of emerging external and internal interference ("noise immunity"). A.F. Wendrich (1974), one of the first researchers in the problem of reliability in sports, believes that the reliability that characterizes the process of implementing quality in accordance with the requirements for implementation can be defined neither as quality nor as a property, but represents one of the characteristics of the process of functioning of any object, and its indicators is the degree of implementation of its inherent qualities in specific conditions in accordance with the requirements for it.

Reliability of an athlete's competitive activity can be understood as a high probability of the realization in a competition of a result corresponding to a maximum or adequate manifestation of functional and special preparedness for specific competitive goals, a low probability of failure in specific conditions of activity (Yu. Ya. Kiselev, 1980).

2 group of definitions combines the definition of reliability of athletes of a particular sport (speaking about the reliability of an athlete, the authors imply the reliability of their activities). Yu. K. Demyanenko, G. A. Pavlov (1980) under the reliability of an athlete understand the degree of technical preparedness and technical resistance to the effects of knocking factors of the competitive environment, which will allow him to perform at a particular competition not lower than a given level.

3 group of definitions combines the definition of reliability of the technical skill of athletes. V. M. Dyachkov and N. A. Khudadov (1977) believe that the most important factor in the system of ensuring reliability is the highest level of technical skill, which determines the level of effectiveness of athletes in extreme competition conditions. They are supported by V.V. Davydov and P.A. Zhorov (1977), arguing that one of the most important components of reliability is the high level of technical and tactical skill of the athlete. It is clear that a high level of real technical and tactical training of an athlete is not a formal, not an external moment of his preparation, it

provides a high level of athlete self-control and at the same time characterizes his attitude to his own reserves and his own capabilities. B. B. Kossov (1977) says that the question of the relationship between mental reliability and the level of technical skill of athletes is of fundamental importance. Essentially, in a competition, a high level of technical skill of an athlete, characterizing the level of his performance, determines the extreme conditions that were mentioned when determining mental reliability. Consequently, the characterization of the level of technical skill should directly be included in the characterization of the mental reliability of the athlete.

4 group of definitions - the most numerous - combines the definitions of mental reliability of athletes. It is advisable to consider the mental reliability of the athlete as part of the overall competitive reliability. Considering, however, that in the real conditions of competitions in the sport of top achievements, it is mental reliability that often determines the success of an athlete or team, it seems legitimate and relevant to special, somewhat singled out, consideration of this issue (T.T. Dzhamgarov, 1977).

It is known that in the general theory of system reliability, two main concepts are usually used - efficiency and reliability. B. F. Lomov, determining the relationship and the difference between efficiency and reliability in systems of this category, emphasized that efficiency mainly characterizes the presence of human properties that are manifested in his activity, and reliability - potential reserves.

The presented definitions of reliability in sports show that: firstly, there is no single, generally accepted definition; secondly, some researchers consider reliability as a procedural characteristic of an athlete's activity, while others consider it to be productive; thirdly, it emphasizes only that aspect of reliability by which it can be quantified, namely the reliability of competitive activity. And there is no answer to the question "What contributes to this?" In the definitions. Fourthly, most researchers rightly emphasize the complexity and complexity of the concept of reliability in sports, highlighting in it either competitive reliability, or the reliability of technical skill, or mental reliability.

The implementation of the general definition is embodied in a special (in relation to sports) competitive reliability, by which we mean the athlete's systemic, integrated, integrated quality, which allows him to compete effectively in important

competitions for a certain time. In addition to competitive reliability, other types of reliability can be distinguished. Structural and systemic reliability — the systemic quality of the athlete's morphological systems, allowing him to effectively overcome physical and mental stress in extreme sports conditions. Functional reliability is the systemic quality of the functional systems of the athlete's body, allowing him to effectively overcome physical and mental stress in extreme conditions of sports activity. Information reliability is the systemic quality of the athlete's psyche to receive information, process it and make optimal, effective decisions in extreme conditions of sports activity. Reliability of sports activity is a systematic, integral, integrated characteristic of an athlete's activity, provided by its systemic-structural, functional and informational types of reliability and realized due to moral and political reliability in the stable performance of sportsman performances in extreme conditions of responsible competitions.

Factors determining the reliability of an athlete Reliability as a complex complex quality of an athlete, determining factors: biochemical, biomedical, psychological and moral. Speaking about the factors that determine the reliability of the competitive activity of athletes, it is worth highlighting the moral factor. The biomechanical factor determines the kinematic aspect of the activity, that is, it ensures the reliability of technology. In biomechanical analysis, it is especially important to identify the leading elements of technology that determine the effective implementation of the entire system of movements.

The role of the biomedical factor is shown in the work of many researchers studying the problem of physiological reserves of the body. The biomedical factor includes: the state of health of the athlete; legal capacity of the central nervous system and analyzer systems. The psychological factor is one of the most important in determining the reliability of an athlete. The implementation of complex techniques is impossible without mental regulation. It is known that a high level of mental stress significantly affects the functional changes in the internal systems of the body.

Reliability can be controlled by acting on all these related groups of factors. The largest number of reliability studies are aimed at studying the psychological factor, which is extremely important for ensuring reliability, as a complex integral quality. The reasons for this are an increase in the level of physical and mental stress in training, increased responsibility for the results of performances in

competitions, the huge neuropsychic tension of the competition, the increasing complexity of the relationship between members of sports teams, the impact of various negative psychogenic factors causing anxiety and anxiety.

At the same time, there are several groups of reasons that cause a decrease in mental reliability in sports:

1. insufficiently high moral and political qualities, low motivation for sports performance, to achieve victory;
2. asthenization due to an unfavorable functional state due to various diseases, fatigue, violation of the work regime, training and rest, and so on;
3. an unfavorable emotional state due to a temporary decrease in the stability of mental processes.

The study of such a factor of reliability as volitional efforts is also inevitably associated with the necessary analysis of the difficulties caused in the process of preparation and performance.

Reliability also depends on three factors:

1. independence and social courage in judgments and actions;
2. ability to withstand stress;
3. power motivation to achieve group goals, a high level of claims and the strength of the system.

Thus, the problem of reliability in sports is extremely complex, and its study must be approached from a systematic, integrated perspective, taking into account all the factors determining it.

Personal characteristics of shooters as a factor in the reliability of their activities
One of the significant factors in the reliability of sports activities is the personal characteristics of athletes.

The analysis of personal properties at the general level means the need to isolate their general psychological mechanism, which acts as a special integral, systemic quality that ensures the reliability of the shooters. The analysis of personal properties at the special level shows how this general psychological mechanism manifests itself depending on the characteristics of various types of sports activities, i.e. various sports. The level of unity in personal characteristics indicates the unique and typical for this athlete modes of action, due to his natural and social development.

The deep interconnection of the general, the special, and the single is the fundamental methodological

principle for considering this factor, which determines the reliability of highly skilled shooters.

Sports psychologists have attached and attach great importance to volitional effort. Indeed, any mental activity, whether perception or thinking, requires effort, and the more, the more complex the activity. The effort grows in proportion to the growth of difficulties and obstacles to the goal. Self-regulation of will is one of the most important in increasing the reliability of shooters.

Thanks to research [7, 15], the principle of self-regulation (self-control) was confirmed in sports [7], requirements were developed for the formation of the principle of self-regulation in sports of the highest achievements, which provided significant practical assistance to such outstanding athletes, like many others.

The principle of self-regulation is fundamental in the factor of reliability of sports activity. A deep theoretical justification of the principle of self-regulation and its active introduction into the training process of shooters allows us to consider it not from narrow, purely sporting positions, but from the perspective of broader, social, psychological and psychological ones.

Only a set of general and specialized features of the psychological warehouse characterizes the active personality of athletes and the individual uniqueness of his athletic talent. It is known that in the analysis of the neurophysiology of anxiety, some authors distinguish its various types. So, some scientists adhere to the point of view of the existence of two relatively independent activating systems: the reticular, activating the cerebral cortex, and limbic, associated with the emotionally motivational aspects of behavior and the activity of the autonomic nervous system.

In accordance with Eysenck's ideas, there are individual differences in the reactivity of activated systems, determined genetically. These differences are the basis of two basic properties (factors) of the personality: neuroticism (anxiety), intra - extraversion. Introversion correlates with a high level of cortical activation, and, therefore, with a high ability to determine the degree of sociability.

Unstable introverts are prone to the so-called conditioned reflex anxiety, which is called mental. Unstable extroverts are dominated by autonomic anxiety systems, the so-called somatic anxiety.

This conclusion is confirmed by studies [7], which revealed that in the psychological mechanisms of noise immunity, the central position is occupied by attention stability, individual stability of the concentration duration, emotional and sensory stability, and the strength of nervous processes. Other parameters studied - balance of the nervous system, neurotism, emotional-motor resistance and extroversion show only tendencies towards a connection with psycho-resistance. Electroencephalographic studies according to the quantitative analysis of synchronously working departments of the cerebral cortex confirmed these findings.

The main types and properties of attention as one of the components of the mental reliability of high-skilled shooters
Attention is the focus and concentration of consciousness on something: an object, phenomenon, action, thought. The direction of consciousness is a set of some objects that are of interest to a person at the moment, out of many concentration is a distraction from everything that is not related to the selected object. Due to these two features, attention is always selective. A feature of attention is that it does not exist by itself, outside of actions (perceptive, mental, motor). Therefore, attention can be characterized "as a working condition". Attention provides clarity and distinctive perception by students of educational material, the speed and clarity of their thinking, and control over the physical exercise performed. An attentive student observes in the exercise and teacher's explanation such details that inattentive students miss.

Attention as a mental process is reflected in specific changes in the biocurrents of the brain, as well as in vegetatics - in respiration and the activity of the cardiovascular system. There are two types of attention: unintentional (involuntary) and intentional (arbitrary).

Unintentional activation of attention is associated with the impact on the sensory organs of external stimuli that cause an indicative reaction. The ease of its occurrence depends on the strength, novelty and contrast of irritating stimuli attract more attention than weak ones, and it matters not so much the absolute strength as the relative orientational silence among the silence can occur to a weak sound (in contrast).

A new stimulus also attracts much attention than an acquaintance. Novelty often consists in changing the characteristics of an already known stimulus. In the

same way, a decrease in the volume of speech, up to its complete cessation, also acts.

Changing the position of an object in space also gives the effect of novelty of perception, therefore moving objects attract more attention than stationary ones. Intentional activation of attention is associated with arbitrary mechanisms and, therefore, with the application of volitional effort to direct attention to a particular object, to change the intensity of attention. The role of volitional effort becomes especially noticeable when there are difficulties in concentrating on the training task.

Attention can be directed to external signals and to oneself, to one's thoughts, experiences, feelings, movements. In this regard, distinguish external and internal attention. External attention is expressed in alertness, vigilance, readiness for action. External attention is also called perceptual. Perceptual attention is associated with motor inhibition, with a decrease in sensitivity to extraneous stimuli. The state of operational rest can be seen by looking at the athletes who are preparing to take the start.

Internal attention is characterized by depth, focus on one's feelings, on the subject of reflection. A typical example of this kind of attention is the concentration of the shooter before the exercise, when he repeats the key points of the correct shot. External and internal attention inhibit each other: it is impossible to be equally focused simultaneously on external signals and on internal sensations or thoughts. Therefore, it is difficult for schoolchildren to do two tasks at once: to follow the teacher's demonstration and explanation of the exercise and to immediately do it, controlling movements.

At the initial stage of training, unintentional activation of attention associated with the impact on the sensory organs of external stimuli that cause an oriented reaction is of greater importance. For example, when studying elements of the shooting technique, the trainer uses such techniques: alternating the story and practical implementation, studying the element, and using visual aids. In addition, when studying the material part of a weapon, it is useful to accompany the explanation with a demonstration of the operation of parts and mechanisms, since moving objects attract more attention than stationary ones.

Nevertheless, if the trainer uses only involuntary attention in training, then the students will not be able to keep intentional attention for a long time, and the lesson will turn from a student into an entertaining

one. For example, when studying the same elements of the shooting technique, the coach reasonably proves the importance of the material being studied, students offer a strong-willed effort to direct attention to one or another aspect of the studied topic.

In addition, attention is focused on focus. External and internal attention is updated during training, depending on the tasks that arise. As a rule, these types of attention alternate. For example, when learning a new position for shooting, students receive the necessary information from the trainer, creating an indicative basis for activity. Moreover, their external attention prevails.

When students, consolidating the acquired skills, perform exercises on their own, then they mentally plan it, repeat it or control its implementation by proprioceptive sensation. In this case, inner attention prevails.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, to the above we give the statement of the first researcher of the personality aspects of the mental reliability of shooters V.E. Milman: "If an athlete has good self-control, even and strong motivation, then anxiety can not only be compensated, but also play a positive role." This position confirms a great individuality (separately), which combines both the general and the special. It is in the individual that the athlete's personality finds its full expression, its main features, the psychic personality trait. Thus, the consideration of the personality characteristics of shooters as a factor in the reliability of sports activity from the methodological positions of the general, the special and the individual allows us to conclude that: 1) the principle of self-regulation, or rather, self-regulation as a personality characteristic of the shooter, acts as a category of general in this factor. Self-regulation is considered from the socio-psychological and psychological positions of the formation of an active, active personality of an athlete;

2) as a special category, the most characteristic representatives of different sports are symptom complexes of personal characteristics that contribute to increasing the reliability of athletes in extreme conditions of responsible competitions;

3) in the individual category, the above-mentioned sides are special (symptom complexes of personality traits of representatives of various sports) and general (self-regulation as a personality characteristic).

The category of an individual involves considering the formation of an active personality of shooters

from the position of an "individual style of activity" as harmonizing the development of an athlete's individual.

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